

1 A Gaussian-Mixture based stochastic framework for the
2 interpretation of spatial heterogeneity in multimodal fields

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5 **Abstract**

6 We provide theoretical formulations enabling characterization of spatial distributions of variables
7 (such as, e.g., conductivity/permeability, porosity, vadose zone hydraulic parameters, and reaction
8 rates) that are typical of hydrogeological and/or geochemical scenarios associated with randomly
9 heterogeneous geomaterials and are organized on various scales of heterogeneity. Our approach
10 and ensuing formulations embed the joint assessment of the probability distribution of a target
11 variable, Y , and its associated spatial increments, ΔY , taken between locations separated by any
12 given distance (or lag). The spatial distribution of Y is interpreted through a bimodal Gaussian
13 mixture model. The modes of the latter correspond to an indicator random field which is in turn
14 related to the occurrence of different processes and/or geomaterials within the domain of observation.
15 The distribution of each component of the mixture is governed by a given length scale driving the
16 strength of its spatial correlation. Our model embeds within a unique theoretical framework the
17 main traits arising in a stochastic analysis of these systems. These include *(i)* a slight to moderate
18 asymmetry in the distribution of Y and *(ii)* the occurrence of a dominant peak and secondary peaks

19 in the distribution of ΔY whose importance changes with lag together with the moments of the
20 distribution. This causes the probability distribution of increments to scale with lag in way that
21 is consistent with observed experimental patterns. We analyze the main features of the modeling
22 and parameter estimation framework through a set of synthetic scenarios. We then consider two
23 experimental datasets associated with different processes and observation scales. We start with an
24 original dataset comprising microscale reaction rate maps taken at various observation times. These
25 are evaluated from Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) imaging of the surface of a calcite crystal in
26 contact with a fluid and subject to dissolution. Such recent high resolution imaging techniques
27 are key to enhance our knowledge of the processes driving the reaction. The second dataset is
28 a well established collection of Darcy-scale air-permeability data acquired by Tidwell and Wilson
29 (1999)[Water Resour Res, 35, 3375–3387] on a block of volcanic tuff through minipermeameters
30 associated with various measurement scales.

31 1 Introduction

32 An assumption that often underlies stochastic analyses of hydrogeological, geochemical, or other
33 Earth system quantities of interest is that these can be depicted as Gaussian random fields. Oth-
34 erwise, sets of observations of a broad range of variables are characterized by sample probability
35 distributions associated with distinctive traits that are not compatible with those typical of Gaus-
36 sian fields. Of particular interest to our study are the following documented patterns: (*i*) the
37 multimodal behavior of probability density function (PDF) of a given quantity, Y , emerging at cer-
38 tain scales of inspection, and (*ii*) the observation that the shape of the PDF of (spatial) increments
39 of Y , $\Delta Y(\mathbf{s}) = Y(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{s}) - Y(\mathbf{x})$ evaluated over the separation distance (or lag) \mathbf{s} , tends to change
40 with lag.

41 In this context, a scaling behavior of the sample distribution of increments has been observed

42 for several variables. For example, permeability (Painter, 1996; Riva et al., 2013), porosity (Painter,
43 1996; Guadagnini et al., 2014), hydraulic conductivity (Liu and Molz, 1997; Guadagnini et al.,
44 2013; Meerschaert et al., 2004), and mineral dissolution rates observed at the microscale (Siena
45 et al., 2021) are documented to be characterized by distributions of incremental values (ΔY) whose
46 moments and main traits vary with s in a way that is not consistent with the assumption that Y be
47 modeled as a Gaussian field. With specific reference to hydrogeological settings, when considering
48 a porous medium whose internal architecture comprises different zones (or regions), each associated
49 with a given geomaterial, attributes such as conductivity/permeability within each region can be
50 viewed as characterized by a unimodal distribution (see, e.g., Winter et al., 2003 and references
51 therein). In this context, Riva et al. (2015) and Guadagnini et al. (2018) suggested that the way
52 the PDF of spatial increments of porosity and permeability scale with lag can be captured through
53 a Generalized Sub-Gaussian (GSG) model. The latter embeds the Gaussian model as a special case.
54 A similar approach has been adopted by Siena et al. (2020, 2021) in the context of their statistical
55 analyses of mineral dissolution rates observed at the micro-scale through the use of modern Vertical
56 Scanning Interferometry (VSI) and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM).

57 Otherwise, conductivity fields in geologic media have sometimes been modeled upon relying on
58 a multimodal distribution (see, e.g., Winter et al., 2003 and references therein). Since the early
59 work of Journel (1983), Desbarats (1987), Rubin and Journel (1991), or Rubin (1995), this behavior
60 has been recognized to arise from a homogenization within a unique population of conductivity
61 values that are otherwise linked to regions characterized by differing geological attributes. In this
62 framework, a stochastic approach based on a model encompassing a unique scale of heterogeneity
63 might not be adequate to represent such composite media within which various processes and/or
64 geomaterials coexist across a given spatial window of observation.

65 A description of a spatial random field as a statistically stationary system characterized through

66 a multimodal model entails considering (*i*) the random geometry of the various regions (or clusters)
67 identified across the system and (*ii*) the spatial distribution of the quantity of interest within each
68 of these regions (Winter et al., 2003). In this setting, Rubin and Journel (1991) view the random
69 function of interest, $Y(\mathbf{x})$, as a sum of $m = 1, \dots, M$ Gaussian components, $Y_m(\mathbf{x})$, each weighted
70 by a (statistically homogeneous random) indicator function. These authors associate the latter with
71 the spatial distribution of the M zones/clusters across the domain. Each random field $Y_m(\mathbf{x})$ is
72 described through its spatial structure and is typically assumed to be independent from the others
73 and from the indicator function. Rubin (1995) considers a porous system composed by $M = 2$
74 distinct geomaterials and provides analytical formulations for the first two statistical moments (i.e.,
75 mean and variance) and for the covariance of $Y(\mathbf{x})$. Lu and Zhang (2002) further extend the above
76 mentioned studies to include in the theoretical formulation a relationship between the covariance
77 structure of the indicator and a characteristic length describing the spatial arrangement of the zones
78 associated with the various geomaterials. Such a length scale is characterized using a Markov chain
79 model, as expressed by Carle and Fogg (1997). Recent applications of these concepts are illustrated
80 by, e.g., Dai et al. (2020), to assess the impact of the internal architecture of a sedimentary porous
81 medium on solute plume dispersion; Gournelos et al. (2020), for the interpretation of the statistical
82 behavior of monthly water discharge and suspended sediment load; and Jia et al. (2022) for the
83 simulation of synthetic long-term time series of streamflow data.

84 Our study aims at extending the theoretical framework underpinning a stochastic description of
85 a composite random field through a stationary multimodal distribution. In this broad framework,
86 we derive rigorous formulations associated with the PDF of spatial increments of a given quantity of
87 interest to embed the observed scaling tendencies of such distributions within a unique analytical
88 modeling approach. In this sense, joint analysis of the PDF of data and their increments within
89 a unique theoretical framework that ensures consistency between these two types of information

90 yields improved characterization of the quantity under investigation. For the purpose of our study,
91 we limit the theoretical formulations to a bimodal Gaussian mixture (GMIX). We then provide a
92 general procedure for the estimation of all parameters embedded in the GMIX model. We explore the
93 benefit of our approach upon applying the ensuing theoretical analysis to interpret two experimental
94 datasets. These represent different processes and scales of observation and are characterized by stark
95 bimodal traits.

96 The first experimental dataset considered comprises a collection of reaction rate maps that we
97 obtain from direct observation of (microscale) surface topography of a calcite crystal subject to
98 dissolution. Detailed fundamental knowledge about these types of dissolution/precipitation pro-
99 cesses is usually demanded in the context of modeling of hydrogeochemical system dynamics. High
100 resolution imaging techniques such as AFM or VSI enable direct observation of the processes tak-
101 ing place at the solid-fluid interface of a mineral. These experimental techniques have contributed
102 to markedly enhance our understanding about reaction kinetics (see, e.g., Lüttge et al., 2019 and
103 references therein). Experimental observations reveal that dissolution/precipitation processes at
104 the microscale are affected by a wide variety of factors. These include, e.g., defects in the crystal
105 lattice or inclusions (Fischer et al., 2014), which result in a remarkable heterogeneity in the reac-
106 tion kinetics. Several authors (Lüttge et al., 2013, 2019; Fischer et al., 2012, 2014) suggest to rely
107 on a stochastic approach and treat reaction rates as random fields. Some preliminary studies on
108 stochastic characterizations are available. These are based, e.g., on a Generalized Extreme Value
109 (Brand et al., 2017) or a GSG (Siena et al., 2021) model. Otherwise, further work is needed to
110 comprehensively address the complex system behavior documented at such scales. In this setting,
111 observed bimodal (or multimodal) traits of the PDF of reaction rates are linked to the occurrence
112 of diverse mechanisms of dissolution of the solid surface in contact with the reacting fluid. As we
113 show in Section 4.1, these mechanisms give rise to distinct regions across the observation domain.

114 The relative proportion of these zones evolves in time and imprints the parameters characterizing
115 the ensuing bimodal random field of reaction rates.

116 We then consider a dataset representative of a Darcy-scale collection of air-permeability data
117 (Tidwell and Wilson, 1999, 2002). These are acquired on the faces of a block of volcanic tuff
118 through four minipermeameters having different inner radius. As such, each dataset is related to
119 a given measurement/observation scale. Tidwell and Wilson (1999) show that log-permeability
120 values sampled across the whole domain of investigation are characterized by a bimodal frequency
121 distribution. The latter becomes more and more manifest as the scale of observation increases.

122 Our study is structured as follows. Section 2 illustrates the theoretical formulation of the GMIX
123 model and our original developments associated with the probability distributions of incremental
124 values of a bimodal Gaussian random field. In Section 3 we propose a parameter estimation procedure
125 and test it on a collection of synthetically generated GMIX fields. Section 4 illustrates the analysis
126 and interpretation of the two experimental datasets described above through the GMIX model. Our
127 conclusions are presented in Section 5.

128 **2 Stochastic model framework**

129 **2.1 Multimodal Gaussian Mixture**

130 We consider $Y(\mathbf{x})$ to be a spatial random field exhibiting multimodal behavior across a given domain
131 of interest, described as (e.g., Rubin, 1995; Lu and Zhang, 2002; Dai et al., 2020)

$$132 \quad Y(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{m=1}^M I_m(\mathbf{x}) Y_m(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1)$$

133 where M is the number of independent and mutually-exclusive modes (or components) of $Y(\mathbf{x})$,
134 $Y_m(\mathbf{x})$ is the m -th component evaluated at (vector) location \mathbf{x} , and I_m is an indicator random

135 field independent of Y_m and defined as

$$136 \quad I_m(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if component } m \text{ occurs at } \mathbf{x} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

137 Note that I_m follows a Bernoulli distribution with mean $p_m(\mathbf{x}) = E\{I_m(\mathbf{x})\}$ (which corresponds to
 138 the relative proportion of I_m across the domain, under ergodic conditions, $E\{\cdot\}$ denoting ensemble
 139 expectation), and variance $\text{Var}\{I_m(\mathbf{x})\} = p_m(\mathbf{x})(1 - p_m(\mathbf{x}))$. Note also that the following constraint
 140 is satisfied

$$141 \quad \sum_{m=1}^M I_m(\mathbf{x}) = 1, \quad (3)$$

142 at any location \mathbf{x} in the system.

143 Focusing on a bimodal field (i.e., $M = 2$), Eq. (1) reduces to

$$144 \quad Y(\mathbf{x}) = I(\mathbf{x})Y_A(\mathbf{x}) + (1 - I(\mathbf{x}))Y_B(\mathbf{x}), \quad (4)$$

145 where subscripts A and B denote the two modes associated with the random field $Y(\mathbf{x})$. Setting
 146 $E\{I(\mathbf{x})\} = p$, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) and the probability density function (PDF)
 147 of $Y(\mathbf{x})$ are respectively defined as

$$148 \quad F_Y(y) = \Pr\{Y \leq y\} = pF_{Y_A}(y) + (1 - p)F_{Y_B}(y), \quad (5)$$

149 and

$$150 \quad f_Y(y) = \frac{\partial F_Y(y)}{\partial y} = pf_{Y_A}(y) + (1 - p)f_{Y_B}(y). \quad (6)$$

151 Here, $F_{Y_m}(y)$ and $f_{Y_m}(y)$ (with $m = A, B$) are the CDF and PDF of component m of the mixture,
 152 respectively.

153 If each component m of Y is characterized by a Gaussian distribution with mean μ_m and variance
 154 σ_m^2 , i.e., $Y_m \sim N(\mu_m, \sigma_m^2)$, the field $Y(\mathbf{x})$ is a bimodal GMIX, and Eq. (6) reads

$$155 \quad f_Y(y) = \frac{p}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_A} e^{-\frac{(y-\mu_A)^2}{2\sigma_A^2}} + \frac{(1-p)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_B} e^{-\frac{(y-\mu_B)^2}{2\sigma_B^2}}. \quad (7)$$

156 Making use of Eq. (6) the raw moment of Y of order q , $\langle Y^q \rangle$, can be computed as

$$157 \quad \langle Y^q \rangle = p\langle Y_A^q \rangle + (1-p)\langle Y_B^q \rangle. \quad (8)$$

158 Therefore the mean of Y can be derived by setting $q = 1$ in Eq. (8), as

$$159 \quad \mu_Y = p\mu_A + (1-p)\mu_B, \quad (9)$$

160 and central moments of order q of Y can be evaluated as

$$161 \quad \langle Y'^q \rangle = \langle (Y - \mu_Y)^q \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^q \binom{q}{j} (-1)^j \mu_Y^j \langle Y^{q-j} \rangle. \quad (10)$$

162 In particular, variance, σ_Y^2 , skewness, Sk_Y , and kurtosis, κ_Y , associated with a bimodal GMIX field
163 are evaluated by setting in Eq. (10) $q = 2, 3, 4$, respectively, as

$$164 \quad \sigma_Y^2 = \langle Y'^2 \rangle = p\sigma_A^2 + (1-p)\sigma_B^2 + p(1-p)(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2, \quad (11)$$

$$165 \quad Sk_Y = \frac{\langle Y'^3 \rangle}{\sigma_Y^3} = \frac{p}{\sigma_Y^3} (1-p)(\mu_A - \mu_B) \left[(1-2p)(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2 + 3(\sigma_A^2 - \sigma_B^2) \right], \quad (12)$$

$$166 \quad \kappa_Y = \frac{\langle Y'^4 \rangle}{\sigma_Y^4} = \frac{1}{\sigma_Y^4} \left\{ 3p(\sigma_A^4 - \sigma_B^4) + 3\sigma_B^4 \right. \\ 167 \quad \left. + p(1-p)(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2 \left[(1-3p(1-p))(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2 + 6(\sigma_A^2 - p(\sigma_A^2 - \sigma_B^2)) \right] \right\}. \quad (13)$$

168 Eqs. (12) and (13) clearly show that the PDF of a GMIX field can be (i) non-symmetric (i.e.,
169 $Sk_Y \neq 0$) even though each component Y_m of Y is symmetric and/or (ii) leptokurtic ($\kappa_Y > 3$,
170 corresponding to a heavy tailed distribution) or platikurtic ($\kappa_Y < 3$), even through components
171 Y_m are mesokurtic (i.e., characterized by $\kappa_Y = 3$). In the hydrogeological context, examples of
172 bimodal features documented for quantities of interest observed across heterogeneous systems include
173 porosity, conductivity, permeability, vadose zone hydraulic properties, and electrical resistivity (e.g.,
174 Zhang et al. (2005); Zhang (2009); Riva et al. (2013); Guadagnini et al. (2013, 2015); Russo (2002);
175 Li et al. (2022)).

176 The extent of these deviations from a Gaussian behavior is controlled by the difference between
 177 the component means (i.e., $\mu_A - \mu_B$), the component variances (i.e., σ_A^2 and σ_B^2), and p .

178 In order to illustrate the main traits of the field considered, Fig. 1 shows the impact of p on the
 179 PDF (and related statistical moments) of a GMIX field characterized by $\mu_A - \mu_B = 2$, $\sigma_A^2 = 0.15$, and
 180 $\sigma_B^2 = 0.05$. The PDF of Y (see Fig. 1.a) exhibits two peaks and a local minimum located within the
 181 interval $y \in [\mu_B, \mu_A]$.

182 As dictated by Eq. (9), the mean of Y varies linearly with p (see Fig. 1.b, note that μ_Y increases
 183 with p in our example, since $\mu_A > \mu_B$). The variance of Y exhibits a parabolic behavior with p
 184 (Fig. 1.c), as prescribed by Eq. (11). It attains a maximum value at $p = p_{max} = (1 + \alpha)/2$, where
 185 $\alpha = (\sigma_A^2 - \sigma_B^2)/(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2$ (with $\alpha = 0.05$ in our example). This also implies that σ_Y^2 monotonically
 186 increases with p only when $\alpha > 1$. The skewness of Y (see Eq. (12) and Fig. 1.b) vanishes for the two
 187 trivial cases $p = 0$ (where $Y = Y_B$) and $p = 1$ (where $Y = Y_A$) and when $p = p_3^{Sk=0} = (1 + 3\alpha)/2$.
 188 Note that the PDF of Y is right-skewed ($Sk_Y > 0$) for $p \in (0, p_3^{Sk=0})$ and left-skewed ($Sk_Y < 0$) for
 189 $p \in (p_3^{Sk=0}, 1)$. When $|\alpha| \geq 1/3$, then $p_3^{Sk=0} \notin (0, 1)$ and the PDF is right- (for $\alpha > 1/3$) or left-
 190 (for $\alpha < 1/3$) skewed regardless of the component proportions. Fig. 1.c also depicts the trend of the
 191 excess kurtosis ($E\kappa_Y = \kappa_Y - 3$) versus p . It can be shown from Eq. (13) that, in addition to the
 192 two trivial cases $p = 0, 1$, $E\kappa_Y$ vanishes for $p = p_{3,4}^{Ek=0} = 1/2 + \alpha \pm \sqrt{(1 + 6\alpha^2)/12}$. Hence, the PDF
 193 is platikurtic for $p \in (p_3^{Ek=0}, p_4^{Ek=0})$ and leptokurtic outside this range. If $|\alpha| \geq (3 + \sqrt{6})/3$, then
 194 $p_{3,4}^{Ek=0} \notin (0, 1)$ and the PDF is leptokurtic regardless of the component proportions.

195 2.2 Spatial increments of a Bimodal Gaussian Mixture

196 Let Y_1 and Y_2 denote the bimodal GMIX, $Y(\mathbf{x})$, at two (spatial) locations, \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 , i.e.,

$$197 \quad Y_1 = Y(\mathbf{x}_1) = I(\mathbf{x}_1)Y_A(\mathbf{x}_1) + (1 - I(\mathbf{x}_1))Y_B(\mathbf{x}_1), \quad (14a)$$

$$198 \quad Y_2 = Y(\mathbf{x}_2) = I(\mathbf{x}_2)Y_A(\mathbf{x}_2) + (1 - I(\mathbf{x}_2))Y_B(\mathbf{x}_2). \quad (14b)$$

199 We extend the approach illustrated by Rubin (1995) and obtain the joint PDF of Y_1 and Y_2 as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_1, Y_2}(y_1, y_2) = & \Pr \{I(\mathbf{x}_1) = 1, I(\mathbf{x}_2) = 1\} f_{Y_{A,1}, Y_{A,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ & + \Pr \{I(\mathbf{x}_1) = 0, I(\mathbf{x}_2) = 0\} f_{Y_{B,1}, Y_{B,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ 200 & + \Pr \{I(\mathbf{x}_1) = 1, I(\mathbf{x}_2) = 0\} f_{Y_{A,1}, Y_{B,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ & + \Pr \{I(\mathbf{x}_1) = 0, I(\mathbf{x}_2) = 1\} f_{Y_{B,1}, Y_{A,2}}(y_1, y_2), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

201 where

$$202 \quad f_{Y_{m,1}, Y_{m,2}}(y_1, y_2) = \frac{e^{-r}}{2\pi\sigma_m^2\sqrt{1-\rho_m^2}}, \quad (16)$$

203 with

$$204 \quad r = \frac{(y_1 - \mu_m)^2 + (y_2 - \mu_m)^2 - 2\rho_m(y_1 - \mu_m)(y_2 - \mu_m)}{2\sigma_m^2(1 - \rho_m^2)} \quad \text{and } m = (A, B),$$

205 is the bivariate PDF of the Gaussian components of the mixture at the two locations. The joint PDF
206 introduced in Eq. (16) is seen to depend on the spatial correlation $\rho_m = \rho_m(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ of each mode.

207 We recall that, as mentioned above, the two components Y_A and Y_B are assumed to be uncorrelated.

208 Hence, $f_{Y_{A,1}, Y_{B,2}} = f_{Y_A}(y_1)f_{Y_B}(y_2)$ and $f_{Y_{B,1}, Y_{A,2}} = f_{Y_B}(y_1)f_{Y_A}(y_2)$.

209 Therefore, Eq. (15) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_1, Y_2}(y_1, y_2) = & E \{I(\mathbf{x}_1)I(\mathbf{x}_2)\} f_{Y_{A,1}, Y_{A,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ & + E \{[1 - I(\mathbf{x}_1)][1 - I(\mathbf{x}_2)]\} f_{Y_{B,1}, Y_{B,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ 210 & + E \{I(\mathbf{x}_1)[1 - I(\mathbf{x}_2)]\} f_{Y_A}(y_1)f_{Y_B}(y_2) \\ & + E \{[1 - I(\mathbf{x}_1)]I(\mathbf{x}_2)\} f_{Y_B}(y_1)f_{Y_A}(y_2). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

211 Considering that

$$212 \quad E \{I(\mathbf{x}_1)I(\mathbf{x}_2)\} = [E \{I(\mathbf{x})\}]^2 + C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = p^2 + C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2), \quad (18)$$

213 where $C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)$ is the covariance of the indicator field $I(\mathbf{x})$, Eq. (17) can be rewritten as

$$214 \quad \begin{aligned} f_{Y_1, Y_2}(y_1, y_2) &= [p^2 + C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)]f_{Y_{A,1}, Y_{A,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ &+ [(1-p)^2 + C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)]f_{Y_{B,1}, Y_{B,2}}(y_1, y_2) \\ &+ [p(1-p) - C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)] \{f_{Y_A}(y_1)f_{Y_B}(y_2) + f_{Y_B}(y_1)f_{Y_A}(y_2)\}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

215 In the following we derive the analytical formulation for the PDF of the omnidirectional spatial
 216 increments $\Delta Y(s) = Y_1 - Y_2$ ($s = |\mathbf{x}_1 - \mathbf{x}_2|$). Second-order stationarity is assumed for all random
 217 fields, i.e., $C_I(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = C_I(s)$ and $\rho_m(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = \rho_m(s)$. The probability distribution of $\Delta Y(s)$ can
 218 be obtained from the joint PDF of Y as

$$219 \quad F_{\Delta Y}(\Delta y) = \Pr\{\Delta Y \leq \Delta y\} = \int_{y_2=-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{y_1=-\infty}^{\Delta y+y_2} f_{Y_1, Y_2}(y_1, y_2) dy_1 dy_2. \quad (20)$$

220 Making use of Eq. (19) and recalling that $f_{\Delta Y}(\Delta y) = \frac{dF_{\Delta Y}(\Delta y)}{d(\Delta y)}$ leads to

$$221 \quad \begin{aligned} f_{\Delta Y}(\Delta y) &= \frac{p^2 + C_I(s)}{\sqrt{4\pi\sigma_A^2(1-\rho_A)}} e^{-\frac{\Delta y^2}{4\sigma_A^2(1-\rho_A)}} + \frac{(1-p)^2 + C_I(s)}{\sqrt{4\pi\sigma_B^2(1-\rho_B)}} e^{-\frac{\Delta y^2}{4\sigma_B^2(1-\rho_B)}} \\ &+ \frac{p(1-p) - C_I(s)}{\sqrt{2\pi(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2)}} \left(e^{-\frac{(\Delta y - \mu_A + \mu_B)^2}{2(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2)}} + e^{-\frac{(\Delta y + \mu_A - \mu_B)^2}{2(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2)}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

222 The analytical expression of $f_{\Delta Y}(\Delta y)$ depends on (i) variances (σ_A^2 and σ_B^2) and correlation
 223 functions (ρ_A and ρ_B) associated with each of the mixture components, (ii) the difference between
 224 the component means ($\mu_A - \mu_B$) and (iii) mean (p) and covariance (C_I) of the indicator field. Fig. 2.a
 225 shows a graphical depiction of Eq. (21) for various lags, obtained upon relying on the exemplary
 226 set of parameters used for Fig. 1 and considering $p = 0.2$. For illustration purposes, we consider
 227 an isotropic exponential model to describe the above mentioned indicator covariance function, i.e.,
 228 $C_I(s) = \sigma_I^2 \rho_I(s) = \sigma_I^2 e^{-s/\lambda_I}$, (λ_I and $\sigma_I^2 = p(1-p)$) being the correlation length and variance

229 of I , respectively) and for ρ_m , i.e., $\rho_m = e^{-s/\lambda_m}$ ($m = A, B$), λ_m being the correlation length of
 230 component Y_m . Here, for illustration purposes, we set $\lambda_A = \lambda_B = 6$ and $\lambda_I = 6.4$. It can be noted
 231 that the PDF of ΔY is always (i) symmetrical with respect to zero; and (ii) characterized by a
 232 dominant central peak (located at $\Delta y = 0$ and controlled by the first two terms in Eq. (21)) and two
 233 lateral peaks (controlled by the last term in Eq. (21) and located at $\Delta y \approx \pm(\mu_A - \mu_B)$). Fig. 2.a
 234 also reveals that the relative importance of the lateral peaks increases (at the expense of the central
 235 peak) as lag increases. This behavior is driven by $C_I(s)$ and $-C_I(s)$ that are seen to multiply terms
 236 related to the central and lateral peaks in Eq. (21), respectively. As lag increases, $C_I(s)$ decreases
 237 and the difference between the height of the central and lateral peaks tends to be reduced. One can
 238 also see that the correlation functions ρ_A and ρ_B appear only within the first 2 terms of Eq. (21).
 239 Thus, their dependence on lag can only affect the central peak of the PDF of ΔY .

240 Statistical moments of the incremental variables can then be readily evaluated from Eq. (21).
 241 Mean and all odd-order moments of ΔY are identically zero. Second moment of ΔY reads

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \Delta Y^2 \rangle &= 2\{p^2\sigma_A^2(1 - \rho_A) + (1 - p)^2\sigma_B^2(1 - \rho_B) \\
 &+ p(1 - p)[(1 - \rho_I)(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2 + \sigma_A^2(1 - \rho_A\rho_I) + \sigma_B^2(1 - \rho_B\rho_I)]\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{22}$$

243 Since $C_Y = \sigma_Y^2 - \gamma_Y$, where $\gamma_Y = \langle \Delta Y^2 \rangle / 2$ is the variogram of Y , Eqs. (11) and (22) allow evaluating
 244 the covariance of Y as

$$C_Y = p^2\sigma_A^2\rho_A + (1 - p)^2\sigma_B^2\rho_B + p(1 - p)\rho_I [(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2 + \sigma_A^2\rho_A + \sigma_B^2\rho_B]
 \tag{23}$$

246 The integral scale of Y , λ_Y , can be computed by integrating Eq. (23). As also discussed by Lu
 247 and Zhang (2002), λ_Y can be larger or smaller than the integral scale of the two modes and of
 248 the indicator, depending on the value of p , σ_A^2 , σ_B^2 as well as on the correlation of the indicator
 249 field. Fig. 2.b depicts the variogram as a function of lag for various values of p . Each curve
 250 attains the corresponding sill, σ_Y^2 (dashed horizontal lines), for large lags. Consistent with Fig. 1.b,

251 $\sigma_Y^2(p = 0.6) > \sigma_Y^2(p = 0.4) > \sigma_Y^2(p = 0.8) > \sigma_Y^2(p = 0.2)$. It can be noted that the same ordering
 252 holds also for the variogram values at any given lag.

253 The fourth-order moment of ΔY is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \Delta Y^4 \rangle = & 2\{6p^2\sigma_A^4(1 - \rho_A)^2 + 6(1 - p)^2\sigma_B^4(1 - \rho_B)^2 \\
 & + 6p(1 - p)\rho_I [\sigma_A^4(1 - \rho_A)^2 + \sigma_B^4(1 - \rho_B)^2] \\
 & + p(1 - p)(1 - \rho_I) [(\mu_A - \mu_B)^4 + 3(\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2)(2(\mu_A - \mu_B)^2 + (\sigma_A^2 + \sigma_B^2))]\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{24}$$

255 The analytical expression for the kurtosis, $\kappa_{\Delta Y} = \langle \Delta Y^4 \rangle / \langle \Delta Y^2 \rangle^2$, associated with the increments
 256 of a Gaussian mixture can then be derived from Eqs. (22) and (24). We recall that this statistical
 257 moment quantifies the tailedness of the distribution and its dependence on lag is a distinctive element
 258 of the scaling behavior exhibited by the PDFs of increments of a GMIX field. Fig. 2.c depicts excess
 259 kurtosis, $E\kappa_{\Delta Y} = \kappa_{\Delta Y} - 3$, as a function of lag for various values of p . All curves exhibit a monotonic
 260 trend. The value of $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$ is seen to increase (indicating tails that become heavier) as s decreases.
 261 This pattern is starkly consistent with the behavior observed for several Earth and environmental
 262 variables (Riva et al., 2015 and references therein). These results clarify that the increments of a
 263 GMIX field exhibit clear non-Gaussian traits, despite each component of the mixture being Gaussian.
 264 As noted above, they also show that the PDFs of increments tend to change with lag due the action
 265 of the degree of spatial correlation of the two Gaussian components of the mixture and of the
 266 indicator field. Values of $E\kappa_Y$ are also depicted in Fig. 2.c (dashed horizontal lines) and are such
 267 that $E\kappa_Y(p = 0.2) > E\kappa_Y(p = 0.8) > E\kappa_Y(p = 0.4) > E\kappa_Y(p = 0.6)$. The same relative order
 268 is maintained also by the values of $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$. Note that values of $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$ are negative (i.e., indicating
 269 platikurtic distributions of increments) at large values of s for $p > 0.2$.

2.3 Parameter estimation

In our analyses of synthetic and experimental datasets (Section 3 and 4), we assume a given set of N observations to be sampled from a GMIX field, Y . We infer the 5 parameters of Y (i.e., μ_A , μ_B , σ_A^2 , σ_B^2 , and p in Eq. (7)) by relying on a well-established Maximum Likelihood (ML) approach, implemented through an iterative Expectation-Maximization (E-M) procedure (McLachlan and Krishnan, 2008; Gournelos et al., 2020). According to the latter, each iteration consists of (i) the Expectation step (E-step), aimed at evaluating the (posterior) probability that each observation belongs to the mixture components, on the basis of an initial GMIX parameter set (or the parameter set obtained at the previous iteration); and (ii) the Maximization step (M-step), which uses the information from the E-step to estimate the GMIX parameter set maximizing the likelihood function. The algorithm stops when the increase of the likelihood function between two subsequent iterations is smaller than a prescribed threshold. Note that E-M suffers from the typical issues associated with ML approaches, i.e., uniqueness, identifiability, and stability (Carrera and Neuman, 1986). To address the issue of the sensitivity of results to parameter initialization, application of the E-M algorithm is repeated n times, each with a new set of initial parameters. Estimates of model parameters are then considered to correspond to the parameter set providing the highest likelihood among the n runs (McLachlan and Krishnan, 2008). The number of runs, n , is case specific and must be set through a stability analysis of the algorithm output. For the scenario here considered, the selection of $n = 40$ allows evaluating stable estimates of μ_m , σ_m^2 , and p . Additional details are provided in the Supplementary material. Note that this procedure can be employed to obtain a fuzzy (or soft) clustering of the data: each observation is assigned to each mixture component with a given probability rather than to a unique component, as it would result from a hard-clustering approach. It is otherwise noted that the spatial arrangement of the categories must be known to estimate the parameters (λ_I , λ_A , and λ_B) of the correlation functions ρ_I , ρ_A , and ρ_B that drive the statistical behavior of the increments ΔY

294 (see Eq. (21)). This can be achieved by (i) assigning each observation to the mixture component
 295 with which the largest posterior PDF is associated, (ii) compute the spatial increments $\Delta I(s)$ of the
 296 underlying indicator field and the corresponding sample correlation function $\tilde{\rho}_I(s)$, (iii) compute the
 297 spatial increments ΔY_m ($m = A, B$) within the regions associated with each Gaussian component
 298 and the corresponding sample correlation function $\tilde{\rho}_m(s)$.

299 An estimate of $\tilde{\lambda}_I$ can be obtained according to the following two approaches:

- 300 • method 1 - fit $\tilde{\rho}_I(s)$ with a suitable theoretical model (e.g., an exponential model or other);
- 301 • method 2 - evaluate the mean length of the indicator field (l_A , see Section 3) and estimate $\tilde{\lambda}_I$
 302 as $\tilde{\lambda}_I = (1 - p)l_A$ (Lu and Zhang, 2002).

303 An estimate of $\tilde{\lambda}_m$ can be obtained by fitting $\tilde{\rho}_m(s)$ with a suitable theoretical model.

304 **3 Synthetic case study**

305 Multiple realizations of synthetic GMIX fields are generated to provide a transparent assessment of
 306 the reliability of the parameter estimation strategy described in Section 2.3 to be applied for the
 307 interpretation of the main traits displayed by the key statistics and empirical densities associated
 308 with experimental datasets (see Section 4). The generation procedure relies upon: (i) a Transition
 309 Probability simulation approach (which takes advantage of the widely tested code T-PROGS; e.g.,
 310 Carle and Fogg, 1996, 1997) for the indicator field, $I(\mathbf{x})$; and (ii) a sequential Gaussian simulation
 311 framework (based on the broadly used and tested code SGSIM; e.g., Deutsch and Journel, 1998) for
 312 the Gaussian fields $Y_A(\mathbf{x})$ and $Y_B(\mathbf{x})$.

313 A set of $N = 100$ unconditional realizations of $I(\mathbf{x})$ are generated on a two-dimensional regular
 314 grid comprising 100×100 nodes by setting $p = 0.2$ and $l_A = 8.0$ (i.e., $\lambda_I = (1 - p)l_A = 6.4$).
 315 The value of Y in each node of the grid is computed via Eq. (4) where Y_A and Y_B are obtained by

316 two sets of N unconditional realizations of Gaussian random fields characterized by and exponential
317 covariance function with $\lambda_A = \lambda_B = 6$, $\mu_A = 2.5$, $\mu_B = 0.5$, $\sigma_A^2 = 0.15$ and $\sigma_B^2 = 0.05$. Additional
318 details are provided in the Supplementary material.

319 Fig. 3.a depicts an exemplary realization of the GMIX field obtained. Each realization is treated
320 as a dataset to which the parameter estimation procedures detailed in Section 2.3 can be applied.
321 Comparison between estimated and input model parameters enables us to assess the reliability of
322 the proposed inference methodology.

323 Fig. 3.b depicts the binary categorical (i.e., indicator) field that is inferred from the E-M and
324 clustering procedure applied to the synthetic dataset in Fig. 3.a. Given the indicator field and
325 the ensuing sample correlation function $\tilde{\rho}_I(s)$, an estimate of $\tilde{\lambda}_I$ can then be obtained according
326 to method 1 and/or 2 introduced in Section 2.3. Note that one of the categories needs to be
327 characterized in terms of its mean length, l_m , when considering method 2. The white portion of the
328 domain (category B) in Fig. 3.b corresponds to the so-called *background category*. In a categorical
329 random field, this term is commonly adopted to identify the category that fills in the space within
330 which other categories are distributed. As an example, in geostatistical applications associated
331 with hydrogeological scenarios, categories are represented by the various lithofacies of a depositional
332 environment and the background geomaterial is typically associated with the category characterized
333 by the lowest deposition energy (Carle and Fogg, 1997). In our datasets, we evaluate the mean
334 length l_A of the category that is not in the background (black regions in Fig. 3.b, associated with
335 category A) by averaging over all of the connected sets of A (*i*) the length of the sides of the bounding
336 box (see green lines in Fig. 3.b) and (*ii*) the diameter of the inscribed maximal balls (red circles in
337 Fig. 3.b).

338 Fig. 4 collects values of GMIX parameters estimated for all the $N = 100$ synthetic realizations.
339 The average of the estimates is always satisfactorily close to the corresponding input value. The

340 mean squared relative deviation (MSRD) between input and estimated parameter values is evaluated
341 over the whole collection of realizations. On the basis of this metric one can note that estimates are
342 overall more accurate for (i) the parameters of the Gaussian distribution associated with category B
343 (except for the mean value), that occupies a larger portion of the domain as compared to category
344 A and (ii) the correlation scale $\tilde{\lambda}_I$ obtained via method 2 as compared against its counterpart based
345 on method 1. In light of these results, method 2 is considered for the estimation of λ_I in the context
346 of the experimental datasets analyzed in Section 4.

347 4 Application to experimental scenarios

348 4.1 Microscale geochemical dataset

349 The first dataset we consider is an original collection of experimental microscale dissolution rate
350 maps. The dataset is obtained from *in-situ* and real-time high-resolution measurements of topog-
351 raphy, $z(x, y, t)$, of the $\{104\}$ crystallographic surface of a calcite sample subject to dissolution in
352 deionized water via AFM imaging.

353 The spatial distribution of reaction rates, $R(x, y, t)$ [$\text{mmol cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$], can be obtained from
354 the difference between two topography maps associated with two observation times separated by a
355 temporal interval Δt as

$$356 \quad R(x, y, t) = \frac{z(x, y, t) - z(x, y, t + \Delta t)}{V_m \Delta t}, \quad (25)$$

357 where $V_m = 36.9 \text{ cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ is calcite molar volume.

358 Estimates of reaction rates via high resolution imaging techniques such as AFM or VSI provide
359 remarkable insights on the complexity of mechanisms involved in these types of reactions. In this
360 context, calcite $\{104\}$ is widely studied due to its abundance in natural environments and to its
361 high reactivity (Heberling et al., 2010). When exposed to a solution, the crystal surface is affected

362 by a variety of dissolution modes. This results in a marked spatial heterogeneity of the dissolution
 363 rate. Such variability can be aptly interpreted through a stochastic characterization (e.g., Fischer
 364 et al., 2012; Lüttge et al., 2019). The prevailing dissolution mechanism depends on the distance
 365 from chemical equilibrium. The latter is usually assessed in terms of the solution saturation state
 366 $\Omega = IAP/K_s$. Here, $IAP = a_{Ca^{2+}} \cdot a_{CO_3^{2-}}$ is the ion activity product, evaluated as the product of
 367 the activities of the species in the solution, and $K_s = a_{Ca^{2+},eq} \cdot a_{CO_3^{2-},eq}$ is the solubility product
 368 constant, given by the product of the species activities at equilibrium. It is noted that Ω approaches
 369 unity as the system tends to chemical equilibrium. We perform dissolution experiments in far-from-
 370 equilibrium conditions, i.e., $\Omega \in [0, 0.007]$ in our setting (Teng, 2004). Within this saturation range,
 371 calcite dissolves by nucleation of etch-pits, which may form randomly on the terraces of the crystal
 372 and/or in the presence of linear defects in the crystal lattice. For a detailed study of the dependence
 373 of the dissolution mode on Ω , we refer to Bouissonnié et al. (2018) and Teng (2004).

374 Details on the experimental acquisition are provided in Appendix A. Prior to analysis, AFM data
 375 often require a signal processing phase, as reported by Marinello et al. (2010). Following Siena
 376 et al. (2021), we perform a preliminary detrend subtracting the best fitting second order polynomial
 377 function from the raw topography data. This enables us to remove the distortion induced by the
 378 AFM scanning and to obtain the fluctuation of calcite topography about its mean, i.e. $z'(x, y, t) =$
 379 $z(x, y, t) - \langle z(t) \rangle$. Fig. 5 collects maps of z' acquired during the dissolution experiment at constant
 380 time intervals $\Delta t = 13$ min. These provide a qualitative appraisal of the temporal evolution of
 381 the crystal surface during the reaction. We observe two main topography patterns. These are
 382 respectively related to: (i) the spreading of a multilayer (deep) etch-pit (MP) in the bottom left
 383 corner; and (ii) the nucleation, spreading and coalescence of several monolayer (shallow) etch-pits
 384 (mP) taking place on the terrace. As a consequence, topography maps can be subdivided into
 385 two regions, namely *Multilayer Region* and *Terrace Region*. These patterns are consistent with

386 published literature analyses regarding dissolution in far-from-equilibrium conditions (e.g., Teng,
387 2004; Bouissonnié et al., 2018).

388 Similar to Siena et al. (2021), we view the dissolution rate as a random field. We express it as the
389 sum of an average dissolution rate, $\langle R(t) \rangle = [\langle z(x, y, t) \rangle - \langle z(x, y, t + \Delta t) \rangle] / V_m \Delta t$, which is constant
390 across the whole spatial domain of investigation, and a local fluctuation, $R'(x, y, t)$, which provides
391 information about the spatial variability of the reaction rate $R(t)$, i.e., $R(x, y, t) = \langle R(t) \rangle + R'(x, y, t)$.
392 Our statistical analysis is conducted on $R'(x, y, t)$, which is evaluated as

$$393 \quad R'(x, y, t) = \frac{z'(x, y, t) - z'(x, y, t + \Delta t)}{V_m \Delta t}. \quad (26)$$

394 Figs. 6.A.a-d depict spatial distributions of $R'(x, y, t)$ resulting from the difference between z'
395 maps separated by $\Delta t = 13$ min. The corresponding sample PDFs of R' are depicted in Figs. 6.B.
396 All PDFs exhibit a prominent peak at $R' \approx 0$ and a secondary peak for $R' > 0$. From a qualitative
397 standpoint, these results suggest that all points that belong to the same topography region (either
398 Terrace or Multilayer) at times t_i and $t_i + \Delta t$ contribute to the highest peak. Otherwise, the
399 secondary peak is driven by values of rate that are associated with locations that transition from
400 one topography region to the other during the time interval Δt , following the spreading of the
401 multilayer etch pit.

402 The observed bimodal trait of the sample PDFs of $R'(x, y, t)$ is consistent with an interpretation
403 based on the GMIX stochastic framework introduced in Section 2. We denote hereafter as components
404 A and B those associated with the peak at $R' > 0$ and at $R' \approx 0$, respectively.

405 We compute spatial increments of dissolution rate, ΔR , at various separation distances. Sam-
406 ple statistics are evaluated considering omnidirectional increments, with the only exception of the
407 direction parallel to the AFM acquisition (denoted as x in Fig. 5.e), to avoid spurious correlation
408 originated from measurement artifacts. This is consistent with the study of Marinello et al. (2010)
409 who show that AFM measurements are often affected by *stripe noise*, i.e., a distortion of the signal

410 occurring along the principal scanning direction. Figs. 6.C.a-d depict sample PDFs of increments
 411 ΔR for lags $s = 16, 32, 64 dl$ ($dl = 11.7$ nm; see Appendix A), encompassing short and large dis-
 412 tances relative to the size of the domain. All of these PDFs share some common features with their
 413 counterparts described in Section 2.2 in the context of the GMIX framework, i.e., they display (i) an
 414 overall symmetric behavior, (ii) the presence of a dominant peak coupled with lateral peaks, and
 415 (iii) a tendency to change their main traits with lag, denoting a scaling behavior.

416 The GMIX parameters as well as those associated with the distribution of $f_{\Delta R}$ are assessed
 417 according to the procedure detailed in Section 2.3, λ_I being estimated via method 2. The analytical
 418 formulations of $f_{R'}$ and $f_{\Delta R}$ (Eqs. (7) and (21)) obtained upon considering the GMIX parameters
 419 estimated at each time are juxtaposed to their sample counterparts in Figs. 6.Ba-d and 6.Ca-d,
 420 revealing a remarkably satisfactory agreement.

421 The analysis of the GMIX parameters at different times provides insights on the temporal evolution
 422 of the mechanisms driving the dissolution reaction. Temporal variations of parameter values are
 423 mainly linked to component A of the mixture. This is related to the observation that the area
 424 associated with category A is subject to higher relative variations than the corresponding one related
 425 to category B , with an average variation of $\sim 36\%$ and $\sim 4\%$, respectively, across the total temporal
 426 window analyzed. The overall temporal increase of p and λ_I (Fig. 7.a and Fig. 7.b) reflects a
 427 progressive growth of the area associated with category A . Such increasing trend is consistent with
 428 the (approximately) constant horizontal spreading rate, ν , of the MP (see Fig. 7.c) evaluated as
 429 (Ruiz-Agudo and Putnis, 2012)

$$430 \quad \nu = \frac{1}{2} (\nu_{ac} + \nu_{ob}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta l_{ac}}{\Delta t} + \frac{\Delta l_{ob}}{\Delta t} \right), \quad (27)$$

431 where ν_{ac} and ν_{ob} are the horizontal spreading rate of acute and obtuse steps, respectively. These are
 432 estimated as the ratio of Δl_i [nm], i.e., the separation distance between etch pit edges at subsequent
 433 times (reported in Fig. 7.d), and the time step Δt [s]. In our case, we can only evaluate the spreading

434 rate of MP acute steps ν_{ac} because no obtuse step fall inside the observation window. It can be
 435 noted that the order of magnitude of the results depicted in Fig. 7.c is consistent with existing results
 436 recently documented in the literature (e.g., Guren et al., 2020; Dong et al., 2020).

437 The mean of both components A and B remains almost constant with time (Fig. 7.e). Otherwise,
 438 a decreasing temporal trend is observed for the variance of component A , whereas σ_B^2 remains almost
 439 constant (Fig. 7.f). The documented pattern suggests that values of the second moment associated
 440 with component A progressively becomes more similar to that related to component B . This is also
 441 consistent with the observed temporal dampening of the multimodal behavior displayed by the PDF
 442 of R' . This trend is also revealed by an observed temporal decrease for Sk_R and $E\kappa_R$ (not shown).

443 The temporal evolution of the spatial correlation structure of each component of the mixture is
 444 inferred from the analysis of ρ_m ($m = A, B$). Fig. 8 depicts the sample spatial correlation associated
 445 with regions A and B . The following common traits can be noted at all times: (i) an oscillating
 446 behavior at large separation distances for ρ_A and (ii) the presence of a nugget effect for both ρ_A
 447 and ρ_B . We relate the oscillations in ρ_A to the small number of points separated by large lags for
 448 region A . Otherwise, the second trait could be attributed to the persisting stripe noise, which might
 449 especially influence short lags. We consider the exponential with nugget as interpretive model for
 450 ρ_m . Fig. 8 juxtaposes theoretical ρ_m values and experimentally-based counterparts. The analytical
 451 formulation enables one to grasp the main features associated with the experimental setting. Fig. 7.g
 452 depicts λ_A and λ_B versus time. An oscillatory behavior can be noticed, in particular for component
 453 B . We relate this trend to the dynamics of the monolayer etch-pits nucleating and spreading on the
 454 crystal terrace.

455 Fig. 9 juxtaposes the analytical curves associated with the GMIX correlation function (i.e., $\rho_R =$
 456 $1 - (\langle \Delta R^2 \rangle / 2\sigma_R^2)$, $\langle \Delta R^2 \rangle$ being evaluated through Eq. (22)) and excess kurtosis, $E\kappa_{\Delta R}$ (evaluated
 457 making use of Eqs. (22) and (24)), of ΔR to their experimental sample counterparts. Theoretical

458 spatial correlation structures shown in Figs. 9.A.a-d exhibit a satisfactory agreement with their
 459 sample counterparts, discrepancies being mainly visible at time $t_7 = 52$ min, for intermediate lags.
 460 Here, we notice that sample PDFs of ΔR evaluated for component A appear to deviate, albeit slightly,
 461 from a Gaussian behavior (not shown). Such a deviation from Gaussianity could also be at the basis
 462 of the imperfect agreement observed between sample and theoretical values of $E\kappa_{\Delta R}$. Given the
 463 purpose of the current study, we envision to further investigate these elements in future works. In
 464 this context, a candidate modeling approach could rely on considering mixtures of Generalized Sub-
 465 Gaussian processes. These have been analyzed by, e.g., Riva et al. (2015) and Siena et al. (2020), in
 466 the context of systems composed by a single region and include the Gaussian model as a particular
 467 case.

468 The results obtained here through the GMIX modeling framework are remarkably promising
 469 for the interpretation of high resolution geochemical data at the microscale. They show that model
 470 parameters are strictly linked to the temporal evolution of the surface features driving the dissolution
 471 reaction.

472 4.2 Permeability dataset

473 We consider a collection of air permeability data acquired by Tidwell and Wilson (1999). Data are
 474 sampled on the six faces of a $81 \times 74 \times 63$ cm³ block of Topopah Spring Tuff. Each face extends
 475 across an area of 30×30 cm² and measurements are collected according to a uniform sampling
 476 grid of 36×36 points (horizontal resolution $\Delta = 0.85$ cm). Data collection relies on four air
 477 minipermeameters, each with a given tip-seal (inner minipermeameter radii, r , being $r_1 = 1.5$ mm,
 478 $r_2 = 3.1$ mm, $r_3 = 6.3$ mm, $r_4 = 12.7$ mm and outer radii being $2r_i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$)). We follow
 479 Tidwell and Wilson (1999) and Siena et al. (2012) and consider the inner radius to be representative
 480 of the measurement scale associated with the corresponding data. As observed by these authors,

481 log-permeability data, $Y = \ln k$, display a bimodal character that becomes increasingly manifest as
482 the tip-seal size increases. Tidwell and Wilson (1999) attribute this behavior to the nature of the
483 tuff, where regions of high permeability (henceforth associated with component A of the mixture
484 model we employ for data interpretation) are associated with pumice fragment, and areas of low
485 permeability (hereafter associated with component B) are related to the background matrix.

486 Here, we focus on permeability data collected on face 1 of the block (see Tidwell and Wilson, 1999
487 and Figs. 10.A.a-d for a graphical depiction) and interpret $Y'(\mathbf{x}) = Y(\mathbf{x}) - \langle Y \rangle$ as a GMIX random
488 field. Sample PDFs of Y' and ΔY are depicted in Figs. 10.B.a-d and Fig. 10.C.a-d, respectively,
489 together with the GMIX-based solution. Note that there is a generally good agreement between the
490 analytical model for both $f_{Y'}$ and $f_{\Delta Y}$ and their sample counterparts.

491 As shown by Tidwell and Wilson (1999), the increase in the tip-seal radius yields an overall
492 spatial homogenization of the observations. This element is related to the smoothing effect of an
493 increasing sampling scale on permeability. Boundaries of the pumice clusters become more evident
494 as r increases. Such a trend is fully reflected by the sample PDFs and by the behavior of the GMIX
495 parameters. We observe a decrease in the proportion parameter, p , with increasing r (Fig. 11.a).
496 This is mainly related to the observation that increasing r essentially contributes to embed (i.e.,
497 homogenize) in region B isolated pixels attributed to component A , thus reducing the number
498 of data assigned to category A . As a consequence, the length scale characterizing component A ,
499 i.e., l_A , increases with r . This leads to a corresponding increase of the correlation scale of the
500 indicator variable, λ_I (Fig. 11.b). The progressive homogenization of the sample fields is also seen
501 to be conducive to a decrease for both μ_A and σ_A^2 , that tend to approach μ_B and σ_B^2 , respectively
502 (Fig. 11.c and Fig. 11.d).

503 We investigate the evolution of the spatial correlation of the log-permeability fields associated
504 with each of the two identified clusters / components upon relying on an exponential model. Modeling

505 results are depicted against sample data in Fig. 12. These results suggest that the modeling approach
 506 we propose yields an overall satisfactory agreement with available observations. We notice that
 507 sample data exhibit oscillations about zero at large lags. This behavior might be captured by more
 508 complex interpretive model, e.g., nested models entailing a hole effect contribution. While this would
 509 possibly lead to an increased number of model parameters, a rigorous analysis taking into account
 510 multiple interpretive models (in a multimodel framework) is beyond the scope of the current study
 511 and will be subject of future works. Fig. 11.e depicts the dependence of λ_m on r . As expected, we
 512 note an increase of the correlation length of both components, following the increase of measurement
 513 scale and ensuing spatial smoothing of the field.

514 Fig. 13.a depicts the sample correlation function, ρ_Y , inferred from the available data and its
 515 analytical counterpart based on the GMIX formulation. These results are complemented by Fig. 13.b
 516 which depicts the dependence of the experimentally- and modeling- based excess kurtosis of the in-
 517 crements with lag for the four available values of r . An overall good agreement between experimental
 518 and analytical results is observed. This strengthens our confidence about the ability of the model to
 519 capture the salient features of the system. One can clearly see that $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$ increases as s decreases.
 520 At short separation distances, values of $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$ associated with a given lag tend to increase with r .
 521 Thus, PDFs of increments at short lags are characterized by heavier tails (i.e., they strongly depart
 522 from a Gaussian behavior) as the observation scale r increases. This behavior is consistent with
 523 the enhanced importance of the secondary peaks displayed by the PDFs of the increments (see also
 524 Figs. 10.C) as well as by the observed increase of λ_I with r .

525 **5 Conclusions**

526 We focus on a stochastic characterization of spatial distributions of hydrogeological and hydrogeo-
 527 chemical quantities which views these as multimodal Gaussian random fields. Our work extends

528 existing formulations (e.g., Lu and Zhang (2002) and references therein) to include in a unique
529 theoretical framework the assessment of the probability distribution of a given quantity of interest
530 and its spatial increments associated with various separation distances (or lags). This enables us to
531 provide a robust characterization of key features of stochastic random fields which are organized on
532 different scales of heterogeneity across the system. These include (i) a slight to moderate asymme-
533 try in the distribution of the target quantity, Y , resulting from the presence of multiple peaks, and
534 (ii) the occurrence of a dominant peak together with multiple secondary peaks in the distribution
535 of increments ΔY . The relative importance of these peaks tends to vary with the lag at which
536 increments of Y are taken across the system giving rise to observable scaling behaviors of the PDF
537 of ΔY . We focus on the particular case of a bimodal Gaussian mixture, whose modes are identified
538 through an indicator random field. The latter is related to the length scale governing the spatial
539 arrangement of zones/regions within which the quantity of interest is randomly distributed. The
540 presence of such regions can be linked to the occurrence of different processes and/or geomaterials
541 within the domain of observation. Each component of the mixture is then characterized by a given
542 length scale driving the spatial correlation of its values and spatial increments within each zone.
543 In this sense, our theoretical framework enables one to infer distributions of quantities of interest
544 through a joint analysis of data about values of the target quantity and its increments to ensures
545 consistency between these two sets of observations. We propose a general procedure to estimate
546 the model parameters, which includes partitioning the domain into the two components of the mix-
547 ture, A and B . The robustness of the proposed methodology is assessed through extensive tests
548 on a collection of synthetically generated random fields. The modeling framework is then applied
549 to interpret two experimental datasets associated with different windows of observation. The first
550 dataset is typical of geochemical applications and comprises an original collection of microscale re-
551 action rate maps evaluated at various temporal instants from AFM topography measurements of the

552 surface of a calcite crystal subject to dissolution. The second dataset is a collection of (Darcy-scale)
553 air-permeability data acquired by Tidwell and Wilson (1999) on a block of volcanic tuff through
554 minipermeameters associated with various measurement scales.

555 Our analysis yields the following key conclusions.

556 1. The analytical expression of the PDF of spatial increments, ΔY , of variables, Y , following a
557 GMIX model displays a symmetric behavior, with a central dominant peak and two secondary
558 peaks. The relative importance of these changes with the separation distance, hence reflecting
559 a clear scaling behavior. This is also documented by the trend of the kurtosis of ΔY , $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$,
560 which increases as separation distance decreases.

561 2. The GMIX model captures the main traits exhibited by both experimental datasets considered.
562 A satisfactory agreement is also observed between sample and analytical statistical moments
563 associated with the increments (i.e., correlation function and excess kurtosis) at different lags.
564 This is particularly evident for the permeability dataset. Otherwise, for the microscale geo-
565 chemical dataset we observe some discrepancies between sample and modeled values for a
566 specific range of separation distances. Here, we notice that sample PDFs of increments of reac-
567 tion rates (ΔR) evaluated for component A appear to show slight deviations from a Gaussian
568 behavior. These deviations could also be at the basis of the imperfect agreement observed
569 between sample and theoretical values of $E\kappa_{\Delta R}$.

570 3. Analysis of the temporal behavior of the GMIX parameters provides quantitative insights on
571 the experimental scenarios analyzed. In the case of the microscale geochemical dataset, the
572 temporal behavior of the model parameters is seen to be closely related to the evolution of
573 the observed dissolution patterns. Having at our disposal a tool capable of encapsulating the
574 dynamics of the physical mechanisms taking place at the solid-liquid interface within a robust
575 theoretical framework that can provide a joint accurate description of the statistics of the

576 variable and its increments can be beneficial to transfer information to other spatial scales.
577 Our analysis of Darcy scale permeabilities suggests that the trend of the GMIX parameters
578 can also be related to the characteristic length scale associated with the observations. Here,
579 the documented behavior of the model parameters reflects the main features associated with
580 the increase of a characteristic length of the measuring device that gives rise, in turn, to data
581 smoothing and homogenization.

582 As detailed in Section 1, several key environmental variables driving contaminant fate and trans-
583 port are documented to exhibit non-Gaussian features (even as monitored within the same geoma-
584 terial/cluster). While Gaussianity of the quantities associated with each cluster is an underlying
585 hypothesis of the GMIX theoretical framework, we envision to extend our work to mixtures of Gen-
586 eralized sub-Gaussian fields. Such fields have been introduced by Riva et al. (2015) in the context
587 of systems composed by a single cluster and include the Gaussian model as a particular case. Ad-
588 ditional elements for future research include (a) the assessment of the uncertainty associated with
589 measurement errors of AFM topography and the way these might affect dissolution rate estimates
590 and/or (b) the exploration of candidate alternatives to be employed in the context of the clustering
591 algorithm, which is a key aspect of the parameter inference framework. In this context, a candidate
592 alternative methodology could rest on a Bayes classifier, which also provides an estimate of the level
593 of uncertainty associated with the data partitioning.

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701 **A Appendix**

702 We employ an AFM (Keysight 5500 apparatus) in contact mode, equipped with silicon tips (Bruker,
703 RESPA-40) and with an Al-coated cantilever (elastic constant $k = 5 \text{ N/m}$) to sample the evolution
704 in time of the topography of the crystal surface. The calcite sample (volume $V \sim 5 \times 3 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$)
705 is cleaved from an Iceland spar (Mexico) along the $\{104\}$ plane using a razor blade. The calcite
706 fragment is placed on a glass slide and subsequently fluxed with nitrogen to remove any remains from
707 the cleavage process. The slide is then secured on the AFM support and a Viton O-ring is centered on
708 the sample to seal the cell volume ($\sim 2 \text{ mL}$). A portion of the crystal surface ($6 \times 6 \mu\text{m}^2$) is imaged
709 with a constant scan frequency (1.41 Hz, scan time: 6 min) along a 512×512 uniform grid, with
710 a horizontal resolution of 11.7 nm. We only consider scans in the top-down direction (Figure 5.e),
711 stopping the acquisition between each imaging frame for $\sim 0.5 \text{ min}$. Therefore, each topography
712 image is obtained within a temporal window of width $\Delta t_a = 6.5 \text{ min}$. Note that in Section 4.1 we
713 evaluate dissolution rate maps across a temporal window $\Delta t = 2\Delta t_a = 13 \text{ min}$. This enables us to
714 detect a significant variation of the area associated with component A , yielding a robust assessment
715 of incremental data and model parameters therein.

716 The cell is open to air on the top and is filled with the solution (deionized Milli-Q water
717 $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega\text{-cm}$). A system of synchronized syringes is connected to the cell. This allows a complete
718 substitution of the fluid in contact with the sample. A volume of 3 mL (~ 1.5 times the volume of
719 the cell) of solution is replaced in the temporal interval between two consecutive frames. This yields
720 (approximately) constant chemical conditions during the whole data acquisition, as documented by
721 the constant spreading rate of the multilayer etch-pit (Fig. 7.d).

722 **Acronyms**

723 **AFM** Atomic Force Microscopy

724 **PDF** probability density function

725 **CDF** cumulative distribution function

726 **GMIX** Gaussian mixture

727 **VSI** Vertical Scanning Interferometry

728 **ML** Maximum Likelihood

729 **GSG** Generalized Sub-Gaussian

Figure 1: (a) Probability density functions (PDFs), $f_Y(y)$, of the GMIX model evaluated according to Eq. (7) for $\mu_A = 2.5$, $\mu_B = 0.5$, $\sigma_A^2 = 0.15$, $\sigma_B^2 = 0.05$, and four values of p . The associated (b) mean, μ_Y , and skewness, Sk_Y ; (c) variance, σ_Y^2 , and excess kurtosis, $E\kappa_Y$, are also depicted as a function of p . Empty circles in (b)-(c) correspond to statistical moments associated with the PDFs depicted in (a).

Figure 2: (a) Probability density functions (PDFs) of increments, $f_{\Delta Y}(\Delta y)$, evaluated according to the GMIX model Eq. (21) for $\mu_A = 2.5$, $\mu_B = 0.5$, $\sigma_A^2 = 0.15$, $\sigma_B^2 = 0.05$, $p = 0.2$, $\lambda_A = \lambda_B = 6$ and $\lambda_I = 6.4$, at four values of the dimensionless lags, s/λ_I . The (b) variogram, γ_Y and (c) excess kurtosis, $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$, are also depicted versus s/λ_I for four values of p . Empty circles in (b)-(c) correspond to the statistical moments associated with the PDFs depicted in (a).

Figure 3: (a) Synthetic realization of a GMIX field with the set of parameters used in Fig. 2; (b) Indicator field associated with the GMIX realization depicted in (a). Green lines and red circles represent the sides of the bounding box and the inscribed maximal balls for a connected cluster, respectively.

Figure 4: Results of the GMIX parameter estimation approach applied on the collection of synthetic datasets generated with the set of parameters used in Fig. 2. Mean of the estimates (dashed lines), input values used in the generation (solid lines) and mean squared relative deviation (MSRD) between input and estimated parameter values are also reported.

Figure 5: Images of fluctuation of calcite topography about its mean, $z'(t_i)$, acquired via AFM at (a) $t_3 = 26$ min, (b) $t_5 = 39$ min, (c) $t_7 = 52$ min and (d) $t_9 = 65$ min from the beginning of the experiment. Scanning directions are depicted in (e).

Figure 6: Dataset and statistical results associated with observed dissolution rate maps, $R'(t_i)$. Colormaps of $R'(t_i)$ (A) evaluated with Eq. (26) from AFM topography measurements depicted in Fig. 5 are shown for the considered times (a-d). Sample PDFs of $R'(t_i)$ (B) and $\Delta R(t_i)$ (C) are also depicted. Analytical results for the PDFs of reaction rate (Eq. (7)) and its spatial increments (Eq. (21)) are juxtaposed to the experimental data.

Figure 7: Temporal trend of parameters of the GMIX model. The evolution of the parameters associated with the indicator random field (p and λ_I) is depicted in (a) and (b), respectively. The behavior of mean, μ_m (e), variance, σ_m^2 (f), and correlation length, λ_m (g) for component $m = (A, B)$ is illustrated. Panel (c) illustrates the horizontal spreading rate of acute steps, ν_{ac} , associated with the etch-pit edges shown in (d) at various times.

Figure 8: Spatial correlation of components A and B associated with the rate maps (a-d) depicted in Fig. 6.A as a function of separation distance, s . The analytical interpretive model, i.e., exponential model with nugget, is also depicted.

Figure 9: Statistical moments associated with the spatial increments of R' . Analytical expressions resulting from the GMIX formulation are juxtaposed to the sample correlation function, ρ_R , (A) and excess kurtosis, $E\kappa_{\Delta R}$ (B) associated with the rate maps (a-d) shown in Fig. 6.A.

Figure 10: Data and results of statistical analyses of (log) air-permeability, $\ln k$, acquired by Tidwell and Wilson (1999) across Face 1 of a Topopah Spring Tuff block. Colormaps of $Y' = \ln k - \langle \ln k \rangle$ (A) for the different values of the inner tip-seal radius of the minipermeameters employed in the experiments, i.e., (a) $r_1 = 1.5$ mm, (b) $r_2 = 3.1$ mm, (c) $r_3 = 6.3$ mm, (d) $r_4 = 12.7$ mm. Results of the GMIX analytical model are juxtaposed to the sample statistics of Y' data (B) and of their increments, ΔY (C).

Figure 11: Parameters of the GMIX model versus tip-seal inner radius, r . Panels (a) and (b) depict parameters associated with the indicator random field, i.e., p and λ_I , while (c), (d) and (e) depict the trend of mean, μ_m , variance, σ_m^2 , and correlation length, λ_m ($m = A, B$), of each of the two components.

Figure 12: Spatial correlation of components A and B as a function of the separation distance, s , for the considered tip-seal inner radii. Results based on the interpretive model, i.e. single parameter exponential model, are also depicted.

Figure 13: Statistical moments associated with the spatial increments of the air permeability data. Theoretical and sample correlation function, ρ_Y , (a) and excess kurtosis, $E\kappa_{\Delta Y}$, (b) are depicted for the considered tip-seal inner radii, r_i